
METHANOL ROOT BARK EXTRACT OF *ACACIA SEYAL* AMELIORATES
CHRONIC UNPREDICTABLE MILD STRESS INDUCED DEPRESSION-LIKE
BEHAVIOUR: INVOLVEMENT OF BDNF AND CORTISOL

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Abstract

Acacia seyal Del. (Fabaceae) is reported to be used in the management of depressive illnesses. The present study was aimed at determining the effect of the methanol root bark extract of *Acacia seyal* (AS) on Chronic Unpredictable mild stress (CUMS) induced brain derived neurotrophic factor and cortisol alterations in mice. Acute toxicity study (LD₅₀) was carried out using OECD guideline 425. The Irwins test was carried out as described by Irwin (1968). The CUMS model was used to induce depression and behavioural tests such as sucrose preference test (SPT), Open Field test (OFT) and tail suspension test (TST) were carried out in mice. The plasma concentrations of cortisol and Brain derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) were assessed using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay kits. The LD₅₀ of AS was found to be ≥ 5000 mg/kg. On CUMS-induced depression, AS significantly ($p < 0.05$) reversed the weight loss, increased the line-crossing activity in OFT and decreased duration of immobility in TST. The AS extract significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased the levels of BDNF and decreased the levels of plasma cortisol in mice. The plant AS ameliorates CUMS-induced depressive like behaviour possibly mediated via the neurotrophic and hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal pathways.

Keywords: *Acacia seyal*, BDNF, Cortisol, Acute toxicity, CUMS

Introduction

Depression is a common mental disorder that represents an important health problem worldwide as it is a known cause of global disease burden and disability (Melchior *et al.*, 2007). According to the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5), the diagnosis of a major depression disorder requires the expression of five or more symptoms for at least two weeks. One of the symptoms should be either a depressed mood or anhedonia (loss of interest). The

other secondary symptoms are weight or appetite changes, sleep abnormalities (hypo or hypersomnia), psychomotor impairment, fatigue or a lack of energy, a lack of concentration, feelings of excessive guilt, and suicidal ideation or attempts (DSM-5).

Chronic exposure to multiple intermittent stressors can initiate cumulative physiological stress responses, called the “allostatic load” (Doan, 2021). The allostatic load is associated with many systemic and psychological diseases (Guidi *et al.*, 2020).

Chronic stress is a psychosomatic process and a crucial risk factor for many diseases such as depression (McEwen *et al.*, 2015; Shehu *et al.*, 2019) and cardiovascular diseases (Kivimaki & Steptoe, 2017).

The Chronic Unpredictable Mild Stress (CUMS) model is commonly used to study depression in rodents, which was first described by Willner *et al.*, 1987. Rodents in this model are chronically exposed to constant environmentally and psychologically unpredictable mild stressors, resulting in the initiation of behavioural changes and potentially inducing depression (Wilner, 1997; Wilner *et al.*, 1992). This model provides a realistic depression model as it mimics daily stressors in human life and induces anhedonia, which is the core symptom of depressive disorder as mentioned in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders IV (DSM-IV) (Guze, 1995; Antoniuk *et al.*, 2018).

Traditional medicinal plants have received recognition and patronage especially in the treatment of mental and psychiatric illnesses (Magaji *et al.*, 2008), with plants like *Acacia seyal* reported to be used in the management of depression in traditional medicine (Shehu *et al.*, 2017). *Acacia seyal* belongs to the family of Fabaceae (Mimosoideae). It is a small to medium- sized tree and up to 17 m tall and 60 cm in diameter, it is widespread in the semi-arid zone of tropical Africa and the Red Sea and from the Nile valley south to Zambia (Kisoi, 2016; Singh & Thakur, 2016). Several studies conducted in recent decades revealed that extracts from the bark of *Acacia seyal* have antibacterial action (Eldeen & Van, 2007), antimalarial effect (Muthaura *et*

al., 2015), antimycobacterial effect, cyclooxygenase inhibition effect (Eldeen & Van, 2008), and anticancer activities (Saeed *et al.*, 2015).

The aim of this study is to evaluate the effect of the methanol root bark extract of *Acacia seyal* (AS) on Chronic Unpredictable mild stress (CUMS).

Materials and Methods:

Animals

Swiss Albino mice of either sexes were obtained from the Animal House Facility of the Department of the Pharmacology and Therapeutics, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria. They were housed in propylene cages and kept under natural day and light cycle. The animals were fed on standard laboratory animal diet and water *ad libitum*. All experiments were conducted according to the Ahmadu Bello University Animal Ethics Committee.

Drugs and Chemicals

The followings are some of the chemicals that were used for the experiment.

Fluoxetine (Mebidos Laboratories Pvt. Ltd, India), Diazepam (Roche, France), Methanol (Fluka-Aldrich)

Plant Preparation and Extraction

The whole plant *Acacia seyal* was collected in March 2018 from Sabon Gari Local Government

Area of Kaduna State. It was taken to Herbarium Section of the Department of Botany, Ahmadu

Bello University, Zaria where it was authenticated by Dr Namadi Sanusi. A voucher specimen (no. 900347) was deposited in the Herbarium of Department of Botany, Ahmadu Bello University,

Zaria.

The root bark extract of *Acacia seyal* collected was dried and sized reduced using mortar and pestle. Two hundred grams of the dried powdered material was extracted with 1500 milliliters of methanol by cold maceration technique for 2 days with occasional shaking. The resultant extract was evaporated to dryness over a water bath which gave a brown solid mass. All solutions for administrations were freshly prepared using distilled water.

Acute Toxicity Studies

Median lethal dose (LD₅₀) determination was conducted using Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD 425) guidelines in rats and mice. In this method, two groups each of three mice were fasted 3 hours prior to dosing. The fasted body weight was determined for each mouse and dose calculated according to the body weight. The extract AS was administered in a single oral dose using a cannula. A start dose of 5000 mg/kg was used for one mouse and observed for 48 hours. The mouse survived, and an additional two mice were dosed and all three mice were observed individually during the first 30 minutes after dosing, periodically during the first 24 hours, and then daily for 14 days. Mice were observed for tremors, convulsions, salivation, diarrhoea, lethargy, sleep and coma. Time of onset of toxic symptoms and disappearance were also noted.

Treatments

The mice were divided into 6 groups of 9 mice each, Group 1 mice were NO CUMS + distilled water (10 ml/kg), group 2 CUMS + distilled water (10 ml/kg), Group 3 CUMS + fluoxetine (20 mg/kg). Mice in groups 4, 5 and 6 received CUMS + methanol root bark extract of *Acacia seyal* at dose of 250, 500 and 1000 mg/kg per orally respectively.

Irwin's test

The method described by Irwin (1968) was used. Four groups of six mice each were used. Group I was given distilled water (10 ml/kg). Groups II, III and IV received 250, 500 and 1000 mg/kg of the methanol root bark extract of *Acacia seyal* orally, respectively. Mice were observed for 48 hours, with more observation within first 4 hours. Observations include morphological, autonomic, neurological and behavioural changes and body weights were taken daily for two weeks.

Chronic Unpredictable Mild Stress

The chronic mild stress was induced by chronic unpredictable mild stress as described by Murua *et al.* (1991). Fifty-four mice were divided into six groups of 9 animals each, matched and assigned to stress and control groups. After three days acclimatization, mice in stressed groups were exposed to the following stressors daily for 4 consecutive weeks. The order of stressors used is described in Table 1.

Table 1: Order of Stressors used to induce Chronic Unpredictable Mild Stress

DAY	FD	WD	WB	2HI	CS	CT	CR	EC	TP
MON	+	+	+						
TUES				+	+	+			
WED							+	+	+
THUR	+	+	+						
FRI				+	+	+			
SAT							+	+	+
SUN	+	+	+						

FD: 24-h Food deprivation, WD: 24-h Water deprivation, WB: Wet bedding, 2HI: 2-hour immobilization, CS: Cold Swim, TP: Tail pinch, CT: Cage tilt at 45°C CR: Cage reduction, EC: Empty cage.

The stressors were applied alternatively so that the mice will not anticipate the occurring stress. The unstressed groups of animals were housed in one cage with access to food and water without disturbance except for necessary procedure such as weighing and cage cleaning.

On day 27 (60 min after drug administration), animals were subjected to different behavioral (TST and OFT). For biochemical investigations, mice were sacrificed by decapitation and brains were harvested. Brains samples were then stored in phosphate buffer (0.1 M, pH 7.4) at -80 °C till further investigations.

Sucrose consumption test

The test was performed as described by Forbes *et al.* (1996). The test was carried out at 0, 2 and 4 weeks of stress. Animals were

deprived of food and water for 21 hours after which they were exposed to drinking water and 2% sucrose. Sucrose preference consumption was calculated using the formula: $(\text{Sucrose intake} / (\text{water intake} + \text{sucrose intake})) \times 100$.

Tail suspension test

Mice were suspended on the edge of the shelf 58 cm above a table top by adhesive tape placed approximately 1cm from the tip of the tail. The duration of immobility was recorded for a period of 6 minutes. Mice are considered immobile if hung passively and completely motionless (Steru *et al.*, 1985). The test was carried out at 0, 2 and 4 weeks of stressors.

Open field test

Each mouse was placed in white wooden open field apparatus (70×70×35 cm,

length×breadth×height) of which one wall is plexiglass. And also, a plexiglass floor divided into 16 visible squares (15×15 cm) with a central square. Behaviour of each mouse such as peripheral and central square crossing was recorded for 5 minutes. Arena was cleaned with 10% ethanol between tests (Rex *et al.*, 1996). The test was carried out at 0, 2 and 4 weeks after stressors.

Sample Collection

Blood samples were collected in plain bottles which were centrifuged at 1,000 x g at 8 °C for 30 minutes. Blood plasma and erythrocytes were separated for cortisol competitive ELISA detection method. Brain was homogenized in PBS buffer (0.01M, PH7.4) and centrifuged at 5000 x g to obtain the supernatant. Brain homogenates were used for sandwich Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay.

Measurement of brain derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) level

Brain derived neurotrophic Factor (BDNF) level was measured using commercially available enzyme linked immunosorbent assay kit (ELISA) kit (Wuhan Fine Biotech Co., Ltd., Catalogue No. EM0020) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The plates were washed 2 times before adding standard, sample and control (Zero) wells. Then 100 µL standard or sample was added to each well and incubated for 90 minutes at 37 °C. After which the plates were aspirated and washed 2 times. Then 100 µL Biotin labelled antibody working solution was added to each well and incubated for 30 minutes at 37 °C. Then plates were aspirated and washed 3 times. Then 100 µL SABC working solution was added into each well and incubated for 30 minutes at 37 °C. Plates were then

removed aspirated and washed 5 times then 90 µL TMB substrate and incubated lastly for 15 minutes at 37°C. Plates were removed and 50 µL stop solution was added to each well. Absorbance was measured immediately at 450 nm using a micro plate reader (Rayto-RT-2100C). The sensitivity of the assay was <2.0 pg/ml of BDNF.

Measurement of serum cortisol level

Serum cortisol level was measured using a commercially available Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) kit (Wuhan Fine Biotech Co. Ltd, Catalogue No. EM1721) according to the manufacturer's protocol. Plates were washed twice before standard, sample and control (Zero) wells were added, then 50 µL sample and standard solutions were added to already precoated antibody plate provided with the kit. After which 50 µL Biotin- labelled antibody was added into each well then incubated for 45 minutes at 37°C. Plates were removed, aspirated and washed 3 times followed by addition of 100 µL SABC working solution into each well then incubated for 30 minutes at 37 °C. Plates were further washed and aspirated and washed 5 times followed by the addition of 90 µL TMB substrate. Then incubated for 15-20 minutes at 37 °C. The reaction was stopped by adding 50 µL of stop solution and absorbance was read at 450 nm immediately using a microplate reader (Rayto-RT-2100C). The sensitivity of the assay was <0.234 ng/ml of cortisol.

Data Analysis

Results are presented as means ±SEM and median scores on tables or figures where necessary. Data for TST and OFT were analyzed using One Way ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) while weight variation were

analyzed using Repeated Measure ANOVA. Bonferoni post hoc test was used to assess significant differences. Data for Irwin's test were analyzed using Kruskal Wallis test followed by Dunn's post hoc test. Results were considered significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Results

The Acute Toxicity Study of Methanol Root Bark Extract of *Acacia seyal*

The median lethal dose (LD₅₀) was estimated to be ≥ 5000 mg/kg orally in mice.

Effect of Methanol Root Bark Extract of *Acacia seyal* on Irwin's test

The methanol root bark extract of *Acacia seyal* impaired changes on locomotor activity (Table 2), motor coordination (Table 3) and diarrhea (Table 3). No death was observed at all tested doses after 48 hours of administration in all the groups.

Table 2: Effect of the Methanol Root Bark Extract of *Acacia seyal* on Behavioural activity

Time (h)	Treatment (mg/kg)	Behaviour			
		Locomotor activity	Grooming	Pain	Vocalisation
0	D/W 10 ml/kg	4	4	4	0
	AS 250 mg/kg	4	4	4	0
	AS 500 mg/kg	4	4	4	0
	AS 1000 mg/kg	4	4	4	0
1	D/W 10 ml/kg	4	4	4	0
	AS 250 mg/kg	3.2	4	4	0
	AS 500 mg/kg	2.8	4	4	0
	AS 1000 mg/kg	2.0*	4	4	0
2	D/W 10 ml/kg	4	4	4	0
	AS 250 mg/kg	3.2	4	4	0
	AS 500 mg/kg	2.6	4	4	0
	AS 1000 mg/kg	2*	4	4	0
3	D/W 10 ml/kg	4	4	4	0
	AS 250 mg/kg	2.8	4	4	0
	AS 500 mg/kg	2.6	4	4	0
	AS 1000 mg/kg	2.2*	4	4	0
4	D/W 10 ml/kg	4	4	4	0
	AS 250 mg/kg	2.6	4	4	0
	AS 500 mg/kg	2.0*	4	4	0
	AS 1000 mg/kg	1.8**	4	4	0

Each column represents the median of 5 animals. Data was analysed using Kruskal walli's test followed by Dunn's post hoc test, * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.001$, significantly different from distilled water treated group. AS=*Acacia seyal*, DW= 10 ml/kg of Distilled water

Table 3: Effect of the Methanol Root Bark Extract of *Acacia seyal* on Neurological Changes

Coordination- Neurological								
Time (h)	Treatment (mg/kg)	Grip strength	Body tone	Motor coordination	Staggering gait	Tremor	Convulsion	Twitches
0	D/W 10 ml/kg	4	4	4	4	0	0	0
	AS 250	4	4	4	4	0	0	0
	AS 500	4	4	3	4	0	0	0
	AS 1000	4	4	2.5*	4	0	0	0
1	D/W 10 ml/kg	4	4	4	4	0	0	0
	AS 250	4	4	4	4	0	0	0
	AS 500	4	4	3.5	4	0	0	0
	AS 1000	4	4	3.0*	4	0	0	0
2	D/W 10 ml/kg	4	4	4	4	0	0	0
	AS 250	4	4	4	4	0	0	0
	AS 500	4	4	3.8	4	0	0	0
	AS 1000	4	4	3.2*	4	0	0	0
3	D/W 10 ml/kg	4	4	4	4	0	0	0
	AS 250	4	4	4	4	0	0	0
	AS 500	4	4	4	4	0	0	0
	AS 1000	4	4	4	4	0	0	0
4	D/W 10 ml/kg	4	4	4	4	0	0	0
	AS 250	4	4	4	4	0	0	0
	AS 500	4	4	4	4	0	0	0
	AS 1000	4	4	4	4	0	0	0

Each column represents the median of 5 animals. Data was analysed using Kruskal walli's test followed by Dunn's post hoc test, * $p \leq 0.05$, significantly different from distilled water treated group. AS=*Acacia seyal*, DW= 10 ml/kg of Distilled water

Table 3: Effect of Methanol Root Bark Extract of *Acacia seyal* on Autonomic Changes

Autonomic Changes and Death						
Time (h)	Treatment (mg/kg)	Diarrhoea (Secretion excitation)	Skin (General)	Colour	Death	
0	D/W 10 ml/kg		4		0	
	AS 250		4		0	
	AS 500		4		0	
	AS 1000		4		0	
1	D/W 10 ml/kg		4		0	
	AS 250	+	4		0	
	AS 500	+	4		0	
	AS 1000	+	4		0	
2	D/W 10 ml/kg		4		0	
	AS 250	+	4		0	
	AS 500	+	4		0	
	AS 1000	+	4		0	

3	D/W 10 ml/kg	4	0
	AS 250 mg/kg	4	0
	AS 500 mg/kg	4	0
	AS 1000 mg/kg	4	0
4	D/W 10 ml/kg	4	0
	AS 250 mg/kg	4	0
	AS 500 mg/kg	4	0
	AS 1000 mg/kg	4	0

Each column represents the median of 5 animals. Data was analysed using Kruskal walli's test followed by Dunns post hoc test AS=*Acacia seyal*, DW= 10 ml/kg of Distilled water

Chronic Unpredictable Mild Stress

Effect of Chronic Unpredictable Mild Stress on Body weight

Changes in body weight in the stressed group were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) as compared to the unstressed group for the duration of 4 weeks. There was slight improvement in body weight in the last two weeks of treatment but was not statistically significant (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Weekly Body Weight of Mice Following Chronic Unpredictable Mild Stress-Induced Depression in Mice

Results were presented as mean±S.E.M. n = 5-9; Data was analysed using Repeated Measure ANOVA followed by Bonferroni post hoc test * $p < 0.05$ compared to the unstressed group. CUMS= Chronic Unpredictable Mild Stress + distilled water (10 ml/kg, *po*), NOCUMS= No chronic unpredictable mild stress, AS= *Acacia seyal* (250, 500 & 1000 mg/kg, *po*), FTX= Fluoxetine (20 mg/kg, *po*)

3.3.2 Effect of Methanol Root Bark Extract of *Acacia seyal* on Sucrose Consumption in Mild Stress

There was no significant difference in sucrose consumption across all groups before stress. However, after two weeks the stressed mice showed significant decrease in sucrose consumption when compared to unstressed mice. After two weeks of treatment, AS (250, 500 and 1000 mg/kg) and FTX (20 mg/kg) did not significantly increase sucrose consumption when compared with distilled water/CMS group (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Effect of Methanol Root Bark Extract of *Acacia seyal* on Sucrose Consumption Following Chronic Unpredictable Mild Stress

Mice were administered AS (250, 500, 1000 mg/kg), FTX 20 mg/kg and D/W 10 ml/kg for two weeks following two weeks' stressor

exposure. Results are expressed as means± S.E.M. (n=9) Data was analysed using One-Way ANOVA followed by Bonferoni post

hoc test $*p < 0.05$ as compared to the unstressed group

CUMS= Chronic Unpredictable Mild Stress + distilled water (10 ml/kg, *po*), NOCUMS= No chronic unpredictable mild stress (Unstressed group), AS= *Acacia seyal* (250, 500 & 1000 mg/kg, *po*), FTX= Fluoxetine (20 mg/kg, *po*)

Effect of Methanol Root Bark Extract of *Acacia seyal* on Duration Immobility of Mice Subjected to Tail Suspension Test

Following Chronic Unpredictable Mild Stress

In the TST, there was no significant difference in immobility time among all groups before stress. However, stressed mice showed significant increase in immobility time when compared to unstressed mice. After two weeks of treatment, AS at the dose (500 mg/kg) and FTX (20 mg/kg) showed significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in duration of immobility when compared with the stressed group (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Effect of Methanol Root Bark Extract of *Acacia seyal* on Duration of Immobility Mice Following Chronic Unpredictable Mild Stress

Mice were administered AS (250, 500, 1000 mg/kg) or FTX 20mg/kg for two weeks

following two weeks' stressor. Results are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M. (n=9), Data was

analysed using One-Way ANOVA followed by Bonferoni post hoc test, $*p<0.01$, $**p<0.001$ = significant difference as compared to the Unstressed group. $^+p<0.05$ = significant difference as compared to the CUMS group

CUMS= Chronic Unpredictable Mild Stress + distilled water (10 ml/kg, po), NOCUMS= No chronic unpredictable mild stress (Unstressed group), AS= *Acacia seyal* (250, 500 & 1000 mg/kg, po), FTX= Fluoxetine (20 mg/kg, po)

Effect of Methanol Root Bark Extract of *Acacia seyal* on Locomotor Activity of Mice Following Chronic Unpredictable Mild Stress

In the OFT, there was no significant difference in the number of lines crossed among all groups before stress. However, stressed mice showed significant decrease in the number of lines crossed when compared to unstressed mice. After two weeks of treatment, AS (250 mg/kg) and FTX (20 mg/kg) showed significant ($p<0.05$) increase in the number of lines crossed when compared with the stressed group (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Effect of Methanol Root Bark Extract of *Acacia seyal* on Locomotor Activity Following Chronic Unpredictable Mild Stress

Values are mean \pm S.E.M. (n=9). Data was analysed using One-Way ANOVA followed by Bonferoni post hoc test, $*p<0.05$

significant difference as compared to the NOCUMS group. $^+p<0.05$ significant difference as compared to the CUMS group.

CUMS= Chronic Unpredictable Mild Stress + distilled water (10 ml/kg, *po*), NOCUMS= No chronic unpredictable mild stress (Unstressed), AS= *Acacia seyal* (250, 500 & 1000 mg/kg, *po*), FTX= Fluoxetine (20 mg/kg, *po*)

Effect of Methanol Root Bark Extract of *Acacia seyal* on Cortisol Levels Following Chronic Unpredictable Mild Stress in Mice

The results showed that the stressed group showed significantly ($p < 0.05$) increase serum cortisol levels when compared with the unstressed group. Administration of AS (250, 500 and 1000 mg/kg) and FTX (20 mg/kg) significantly ($p < 0.05$) decreased cortisol levels as compared to the stressed group (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Effect of Methanol Root Bark Extract of *Acacia seyal* on Serum Cortisol Levels Following Chronic Unpredictable Mild Stress in Mice

Results are presented as mean \pm S.E.M. Data was analysed using One-Way ANOVA followed by Bonferoni post hoc test

*** $p < 0.001$ as compared to the unstressed group, + $p < 0.05$, ++ $p < 0.01$, +++ $p < 0.001$ as compared to CUMS group

CUMS= Chronic Unpredictable Mild Stress + distilled water (10 ml/kg, *po*), NOCUMS= No chronic unpredictable mild stress (Unstressed), AS= *Acacia seyal* (250, 500 & 1000 mg/kg, *po*), FTX= Fluoxetine (20 mg/kg, *po*)

Effect of Methanol Root Bark Extract of *Acacia seyal* on BDNF Levels in Mice

There was a significant ($p<0.05$) decrease in BDNF levels of mice when compared to the unstressed group following two weeks' exposure to stress. Administration of AS (250, 500 and 1000 mg/kg) and FTX (20 mg/kg) significantly ($p<0.05$) increased the expression of BDNF as compared to the stressed/distilled water group (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Effect of Methanol Root Bark Extract of *Acacia seyal* on Brain Derived Neurotrophic Factor levels in the brain of Mice Following Chronic Unpredictable Mild Stress

Results were presented as mean±S.E.M. Data was analysed using one-way ANOVA followed by Bonferoni post hoc test

*** $p<0.001$ compared to the unstressed group, + $p<0.05$, +++ $p<0.001$ as compared to the stressed/distilled water group. n=5-9.

CUMS= Chronic Unpredictable Mild Stress + distilled water (10 ml/kg, *po*), NOCUMS= No chronic unpredictable mild stress (Stressed), AS= *Acacia seyal* (250, 500 & 1000 mg/kg, *po*), FTX= Fluoxetine (20 mg/kg, *po*)

Discussion

Chronic stress is an important factor in depression, and changes in various body systems that occurred in depression are similar to those observed in response to stress (Muscat *et al.*, 1992; Pizzagalli, 2014). Chronic Unpredictable Mild Stress (CUMS), the most promising and valuable rodent model of depression, is widely used to research and screen for antidepressants. In addition, as proposed by Willner and his colleagues CUMS appears more suitable for studying the mechanisms of antidepressant drugs (Wilner *et al.*, 1992). In the CUMS procedure, animals are exposed to different kinds of mild stress every day, which mimics chronic stressful life events and results in anhedonia and locomotor activity decreasing, the core symptoms of human depression. As a result, these symptoms induced by CUMS procedure can be restored by therapeutically effective drugs for the treatment of depression (Wilner *et al.*, 1992; Muscat *et al.*, 1992; Arıcıoğlu *et al.*, 2020).

The present focused on investigating the antidepressant-like effect and mechanisms of AS treatment in this model. Our results showed that CUMS can reduce scores of crossing in OFT, decreased body weight and reduced sucrose preference in SPT while an increase in immobility time was observed in TST, the present result is in agreement to the

findings of other similar studies (Wilner *et al.*, 1992; Dai *et al.*, 2022).

Some of these symptoms induced by CUMS procedure were significantly attenuated by chronic treatment with AS at 250 mg/kg, 500 mg/kg and 1000 mg/kg. The increase in SPT was not significant after two weeks administration at all tested dose levels. There was an increase in the number of lines crossed which was only significant at AS 250 mg/kg.

Decrease in immobility time also significant only significant at AS 500 mg/kg. Changes in body weight was not statistically significant in all tested doses, which confirmed that CUMS can affect mice behaviour and cause depression, AS (500 mg/kg) can antagonise it and has antidepressant-like effects.

It has been established that abnormality of neuroendocrine function plays an important role in the occurrence of depression (Helmreich *et al.*, 2005; Chávez-Castillo *et al.*, 2019). The hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis is one of the important neuroendocrine axes, and enhanced activity of this axis is considered a key neurobiological alteration in major depression (Helmreich *et al.*, 2005; Coric *et al.*, 2010). CRF, the major physiological regulator of HPA system, is believed to contribute to several depressive symptoms, and augmentation of pituitary, and elevated cortisol levels in serum have been observed in depressive disorders (Bart *et al.*, 2001; Bertollo *et al.*, 2020). On the other hand, HPA axis hyperactivity is dependent on a depressed status and it tends to be normalized following alleviation of clinical symptoms after antidepressant treatments (Bischof *et al.*,

2003; Shehu *et al.*, 2019). Thus, normalization of HPA axis activity is a cure key and an indication of depression relief.

In the present study, the CMS procedure resulted in increase of serum cortisol in mice, indicating that CMS might cause HPA axis hyperactivity. It supported the hypothesis that AS could exert its antidepressant effect by normalizing HPA axis hyperactivity through cortisol levels regulation.

BDNF is essential for neuronal plasticity and survival in the adult brain (Mizui *et al.*, 2016). Alterations of brain BDNF levels in the pathophysiology of depression and the

effects of antidepressants depend on brain areas (Yu and Chen, 2011). An increase of the hippocampal BDNF following chronic antidepressant treatment is associated with neurogenesis (Lyon *et al.*, 2011), while the antidepressant action in the prefrontal cortex relates to synaptic plasticity (Sairanen *et al.*, 2007; Andrade and Rao, 2010). In this study, AS and fluoxetine increased BDNF levels in the brain suggesting that AS may be used as a neuroprotective agent against depression.

The findings in this study showed that AS ameliorates CUMS-induced depressive like behaviour which is possibly mediated via the neurotrophic pathway

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